

PLASTIC IS HEALTHY! A QUALITATIVE APPROACH OF THE KANSEI ENGINEERING METHODOLOGY IN MILK PACKAGING

Skandalis Alexandros, Papantonopoulos Sotirios, Koulouriotis Dimitrios
Democritus University of Thrace
alexandros.skandalis@gmail.com, spapantono@yahoo.gr, jimk@pme.duth.gr

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, consumers tend to be eclectic, vary according to their needs and habits and difficult to predict. Feelings and emotions play an important role for the understanding of consumers' hidden symbolic meanings to products and/or services. Kansei Engineering is an emotional product design methodology that aims to capture consumers' feelings for a product and/or service and translate them into design elements. The aim of this paper is to investigate the existing literature within the kansei engineering field and to propose an alternative qualitative explanation of the output of the methodology through its application to the evaluation of milk cartons within the Greek industry.

Keywords: emotional design, kansei engineering, milk packaging, qualitative methodologies, consumer research.

INTRODUCTION

In today's complex and turbulent environments, a new mode of social order is created which is characterized by schizophrenic modes of space and time (Harvey 1989, as cited in Goulding 2003) and where the transformed role of consumption constitutes a major aspect of it. Plurality and fluidity into the practices of an individual's everyday life better represent the current human condition (Firat and Venkatesh, 1993). Consumers have started to buy products not only for their use value but also for what they convey that is symbolic meanings, which express personal values, social norms and cultural ideologies (Hirschman, 1988). Thus, feelings and emotions begin to play an important role for the expression of such symbolic meanings. In this sense, design research and practice are moving from function, form and usability, to

emotional dimensions that enhance user experiences (Norman, 2004).

The adoption of interdisciplinary techniques and methodologies is argued to be extremely useful in order to explore consumers' feelings effectively and better define their needs and requirements towards the design of new products. Affective or Kansei Engineering is a field of product design that aims to understand consumers' needs and requirements by translating their feelings and emotions for a product into design elements (Jordan 2000; Henson et al. 2006, as cited in Skandalis et al. 2011). Tools and techniques from a wide variety of fields, such as psychology, ergonomics, informatics and social sciences, are incorporated within various stages of the methodology (Nagamachi 1995; Schutte et al. 2004). Kansei Engineering aims to grasp the feelings and the emotions (kansei) of a consumer for a product, link these emotions with the product properties and translate them into design elements. In order to understand and describe an individual's kansei, several methods have been developed that evaluate physiological responses (e.g. heart rate), individuals' behaviours and actions, facial and body expressions and most commonly spoken words (Nagamachi 1995; Schutte et al. 2004).

The scope of this paper is to investigate the existing literature within the Kansei Engineering field and to suggest an alternative, interpretive explanation of the methodology, through its application to the evaluation of existing milk cartons within the Greek industry. The specified 'product domain' of the study was the category of light-fresh milk and the selected target group of consumers was undergraduate students aged 18-24 years old. Three main product properties were examined - shape, colour and material - that were identified as the most important during the initial steps of the study. A linkage of the product properties and the generated kansei words was conducted that

led to the development of a final qualitative model that provides useful insights for the design of milk cartons or the improvement of existing ones.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE KANSEI ENGINEERING PROCESS

The word *kansei* originates from Japan and due to its complex meaning, it cannot be directly translated to other languages (Schutte, 2005). *Kansei* is the impression created to someone from a certain artefact, environment or situation using all of his or her senses and cognition.

According to Nagamachi (2001), there are three focal points when applying the *kansei* engineering methodology: a) the understanding of an individual's *kansei*, b) the translation and linkage of his or her *kansei* with the product design process and c) the development of a *kansei* engineering system. The most common part of the *kansei* that is calculated is limited to the part that individuals are able to express with the usage of words. There are six different types of *kansei* engineering developed. Schutte et al. (2004) have proposed a general framework of the *Kansei Engineering* methodology, which follows a six-step process; choice of domain, spanning the semantic space, spanning the space of properties, synthesis, test of validity and model building. An alternative theoretical framework, which includes the investigation of communities of product enthusiasts and the incorporation of several qualitative methodologies, has been recently developed (Skandalis et al., 2011).

The identification of the product domain refers to the definition of the target group of consumers using the product, the collection of all the available product samples and/or the inclusion of new design solutions (Schutte et al., 2004). The semantic space includes the collection of the words that describe the product domain - referred as *kansei* words, the structure and grouping of the *kansei* words and the selection of the final *kansei* words (Nagamachi, 1997). It is proposed that these words are mainly adjectives but other grammatical forms such as nouns or verbs can be utilised, depending on the nature of the research project (Schutte and Ekklund, 2001).

Words are collected from all the available sources related to the product domain, such as magazines, manual reviews, experienced users and so on, and

the process continues until no new words occur (Schutte et al., 2004). Nagamachi (1997) proposed that the total number of words gathered, should be between 50 - 600 words, according to the nature of the product domain.

The next step is the selection of the final *kansei* words that are to be forwarded to the synthesis stage. Two methods are currently implemented in order to achieve effective word reduction (Schutte et al., 2004). The first method includes the application of pilot studies with the aid of Semantic Scales techniques and the analysis of the results with statistical tools, e.g. factor analysis (Osgood et al. 1969; Alcantara et al. 2005) or cluster analysis (Hair et al., 1995). Alternatively, focus groups with users of the product are conducted with the aid of affinity diagram techniques (Bergman and Klefsjö 1994 as cited in Schutte et al. 2004).

In order to define the product domain and collect the required data for the semantic space, the investigation of communities of product enthusiasts can also be employed through the application of observation methodologies such as ethnography or netnography (Skandalis et al., 2011). During the last years, consumption or brand communities have been widely investigated within the consumer research field and might provide useful insights for the formation of the product domain and the development of the semantic space.

The space of properties is the final step before the synthesis stage. The theoretical background here is limited. Schutte (2005) suggests a three-step process- collection, selection and gathering- that follows the same approach applied at the semantic space step. The existing product samples that describe the product domain are collected. Product properties are identified and the ones that will participate in the synthesis phase are selected. Correspondingly, product samples to represent them are gathered. The application of focus groups and depth interviews with users of the products, consumption communities' members and/or design experts can also be applied to facilitate the process (Skandalis et al. 2011).

In the synthesis stage, the connection between the semantic space and the space of properties is conducted. Each *kansei*-word is connected with the product properties. The methods used here are either manual or statistical. Manual methods are Category

Identification - most commonly cited as Kansei Engineering Type I (Nagamachi 1997; Ishihara et al. 1997) and the application of projective techniques with product users (Skandalis et al., 2011). Statistical methods such as Regression analysis (Henson et al., 2006), General linear model (Arnold and Burkhard 2001), Quantification Theory (Komazawa and Hayashi 1976), Rough Set Theory (Nishino et al. 2001) and Fuzzy Set Theory (Shimizu and Jindo, 1995) are applied for the treatment of greater amounts of data. The results are checked to certify that data distribution was normal. The most common methods applied are statistical methods, such as one sample-t-test and factor analysis, and visual checking of the data (Schutte et al., 2004). The final kansei engineering model is the evaluated result of the synthesis phase. Depending on the methods implemented in previous stages, the final model could be either of quantitative or qualitative nature. The output of the model could result either in the design of new products if new design solutions were incorporated at previous stages of the methodology or as a guide for the improvement of existing products (Schutte et al., 2004).

APPLICATION OF KANSEI ENGINEERING TO THE EVALUATION OF MILK PACKAGING

CHOICE OF PRODUCT DOMAIN

There are many different types of milk cartons available at the Greek market. According to the freshness of the milk, each type can be broadly categorized into four main groups: fresh milk, high-pasteurized milk, ultra high-pasteurized milk and concentrated milk. In addition, according to the milk's degree of fat elements, each type is categorized into three subgroups: full-fat, medium and diet or 'light' milk. Desk research, mainly centered on web-based sources, indicated that each combination of the above-mentioned groups of milk, leads to a unique milk carton. The specified product domain applied in this study was the category of 'light-fresh milk'. The target group of participants was undergraduate students aged 18-24 years old, from three major Greek universities of Athens, Thessaloniki and Thrace. Initially, a questionnaire survey was conducted within a sample of 150 students. The survey included questions concerning the type of milk that the participants consume, the milk brand they

prefer, how often they purchase milk and which factors influence their purchasing habits. Participants were also asked to select which product properties, feel that represent better the selected product domain. The average time of filling the questionnaire was two minutes.

The aim of this survey was to give a brief, initial understanding of the milk industry in Greece and the product domain studied. The results of the survey indicated that 58,6% of the participants prefer to consume the type of fresh-light milk and 20,6% of the participants prefer to consume the type of full-fat milk. In regard with the factors that influence participants' choice of a certain milk brand, the most common responses were the quality of the milk and the visual appearance of the carton. The product properties shape, color and material were cited as the most important elements of the visual appearance of the carton.

SPAN THE SEMANTIC SPACE AND THE SPACE OF PROPERTIES

Here, all the words describing the product domain were collected. The initial number of the words gathered was 86 words. During the initial word collection, no critical evaluation of the words was conducted. The procedure of collection lasted approximately 20-25 hours and was terminated when no new words continued to occur. Forums of product enthusiasts and websites of milk companies in Greece proved to be the most useful sources of word collection. The procedure of word collection through forums and websites related to the product domain resembles the process of online ethnographic methods applied in consumer research studies, most commonly cited as netnographic methods (Kozinets, 2010). Netnography or online ethnography aims to investigate the consumer behaviour of cultures and communities that exist on the Internet and can be defined as a written account of online cultures that are mediated by contemporary computerized communications technology and are informed by the methods applied in cultural anthropology (Kozinets 1997; 2001; 2002). In this study, it is advocated that the procedure of the identification of the product domain and of the word collection from all the possible sources located on the web can be characterized as a 'mini' netnographic process.

In order to achieve effective word reduction, the affinity technique process was applied. The affinity process refers to the employment of focus groups where participants are asked to arrange words into groups based on their affinity and select representatives for every group (Schutte, 2002). Words are written and presented into cards to facilitate the grouping process. A focus group of five undergraduate students was generated and moderated by the authors. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and the aim of the focus group. A short explanation of the affinity process was also conducted. The initial 86 words were divided into 41 groups. Words that did not match with others formed a group by their own. A second grouping was generated and 32 groups occurred. One word of each group was selected to represent the group. These words were candidates for kansei words. Finally, 23 words were selected as kansei words (Table 1). The collection of the product properties includes almost the same procedure as the process of word collection. Samples of all the available milk cartons in the Greek market were collected. We managed to collect twelve samples from Greek milk companies that represented the domain 'light-fresh milk'. To avoid any ethical issues raised, an alphabetical naming of the milk companies was conducted. In addition to this, all the possible product properties of these 12 samples were identified. Based on the responses from the initial survey and the insights gained from the 'mini' netnographic process, the properties that were selected to represent the product samples to the synthesis phase were the shape, the material and the color of the carton. Given the available samples within the Greek market, the shape of the carton was divided into three types - cylindrical, pyramid and rectangular. The milk cartons of companies B, H and G were selected to represent them accordingly. In the same

notion, the material of the carton was divided into two types - paper and plastic - and the samples of companies E and A were selected to represent the paper and plastic material. Finally, the colour of light-fresh milk was divided into three types - white, green and blue and the cartons of companies F, C and D were selected to represent them at the synthesis phase.

quality	pure	fresh
light	ergonomic	pasteurized
essential	tasty	modern
dietary	vitamins	beautiful
exciting	home-made	healthy
friendly	eclectic	great
cool	relaxing	preservable
corroborant	unique	

Table 1. Final kansei words

SYNTHESIS AND FINAL MODEL BUILDING

The eight cartons mentioned above, represent the space of properties at this questionnaire with photos (Table 2). The semantic space is represented by the 23 kansei words that occurred from the affinity process (Table 1). A questionnaire survey, based on the concept of differential semantics by Osgood et al. (1969), was conducted to identify links between the selected words and properties. The participants were asked to evaluate the correspondence and influence of each kansei word and property with the product domain "light-fresh" milk, on a seven-grade Likert scale. A semantic differential scale includes two opposing concepts that are separated by a scale (Van

Shape			Material		Colour		
B	H	G	E	A	F	C	D

Table 2. 'Kansei' Properties for milk cartons

Lottum et al., 2006). Participants were also urged to describe how they imagine the ideal carton on the seven-grade scale. The participants were 20 undergraduate students aged 18-24 years old, 10 male and 10 female, from the universities of Athens, Thessaloniki and Thrace. The average time of filling the questionnaire was 40 minutes.

At first, participants were informed about the kansei engineering methodology and the aim of the questionnaire. An explanation of the meaning of the

seven-grade scale and the way they should fill the questionnaire was also provided. After filling the questionnaire, a brief conversation took place, in the form of a depth interview, in order to grasp participants' suggestions and ideas about the questionnaire and the method. The central purpose of group and depth interviews is to get comments about how things are remembered and what they mean for the participants (Thompson et al., 1989). As a result, interviews also helped to further comprehend the

Figure 2. 'Kansei' Properties for milk cartons

Figure 3. Ideal 'Kansei' profile for milk cartons

product domain and support the findings of the observation process (Kozinets 2002; Muniz and Hope 2005 as cited in Skandalis et al. 2011).

Finally, during the filling process about the ideal carton, participants were also asked to indicate those kansei words that they consider to be more important and which properties represent better these words for the product domain studied. The results of the survey were analysed in Microsoft Excel and are presented below (Figure 2 and 3). As seen in Figure 2, there are cartons that achieved high scores to certain kansei words while other cartons achieved low scores. It is indicated that the cartons from companies H and F, achieve the greatest impact on kansei words while the cartons of companies G and C achieve the lowest impact. Furthermore, some cartons were not

evaluated as expected. The cartons of companies D and A scored low in most kansei words.

The diagram (Figure 3) was the result of the feeling of the participants about the ideal kansei profile for milk packaging. The importance that participants place to certain kansei words such as quality, pure fresh, healthy, eclectic, great and preservable is illustrated. On the other hand, participants' perception about the ideal kansei profile is aligned with a low influence on kansei words such as dietary, modern and friendly. In general, it is argued that these initial considerations illustrate participants' emphasis on the safe and health side of the milk.

The final kansei engineering model is based on the analysis of the questionnaire survey and the insights from the initial steps of the study. The model provides

Properties	Material		Shape			Color		
	Paper	Plastic	Cylindrical	Rectangular	Pyramid	White	Green	Blue
quality		+	+			+	+	-
pure			+			+	+	
fresh		+	+			+	+	
light	+				+			
ergonomic		+						
pasteurized	+	+	+		+		+	
essential	-	-						-
tasty		+					+	
modern	+		-	-		-	-	-
dietary							-	
vitamins	-		+	-	-			-
beautiful		+		-		-		
exciting		-	-	-		+	+	
home-made	-		-				+	-
healthy		+	+			+	-	-
friendly				-			-	
eclectic		+		-				-
great				-		-		-
cool		+	+					
relaxing						-		-
sustainable			+	-				-
corroborant								
unique	-	-			-			-

Table 3. Final qualitative Kansei Engineering model

a qualitative output of the selected kansei words and properties (Table 3). The evaluation of the results was conducted with visual checking of the data. Given the relatively low amount of data, this method was selected instead of a more time-consuming one-sample t-test. As shown at the matrix (Table 3), product properties that are deemed to have a positive impact on kansei words are assigned the + mark while the properties that are deemed to have a negative impact are assigned the - mark. Blank spaces illustrate that these properties have a neutral impact on the selected kansei words. Certain assumptions and inferences can be drawn for the impact of the selected kansei words in the product properties of existing milk cartons within the Greek milk industry that can be utilized either for improvement or innovative design solutions.

The paper material and pyramid shape of a milk carton are labelled as 'light' and 'pasteurized' but not 'vitamins'. It is argued that both the paper material and pyramid shape strongly emphasize on the nature of the product domain, 'light-fresh' milk. Milk cartons have been traditionally linked with paper materials and pyramid shapes that represent the most common milk packaging solutions for manufacturers. Thus, it is advocated that this may be a reason why the paper material was not thought as being 'unique' and 'essential' and of being 'modern' but not 'home-made'. The plastic material is deemed 'quality', 'fresh', 'pasteurized', 'tasty', 'ergonomic', 'healthy' and 'eclectic'. It is thought that the plastic material aims to enhance the concept of the product domain studied and create a feeling of 'healthiness' of the product consumed and focus on the product itself, possibly due to its transparent nature. The same assumption also applies to the cylindrical shape and the colors, white and green, that were labeled as 'healthy', 'fresh', 'quality', 'pure', etc. However, unlike the white and green colour, the cylindrical shape was not regarded as 'exciting' and 'home-made'. Interestingly, the rectangular shape and the blue colour did not create any positive feelings to the participants in any kansei words. On the other hand, they are thought as being far from the notion of a 'healthy' and 'friendly' milk carton.

Finally, it is important to mention that no product properties were thought as being 'unique' and/or 'essential'. It is maintained that this is revelatory of the

state of the milk packaging industry in Greece that lacks of innovative design solutions.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this piece of research was to provide a theoretical overview of the kansei engineering process up to date and to suggest an interpretive explanation of the output of the methodology. The final model is of qualitative nature and provides certain connections between the kansei words and the product properties investigated.

In regard with the case of study, that is the evaluation of existing packaging within the Greek milk industry, it is advocated that the model leads to certain assumptions for the 'kansei' feeling of the participants in relation with the evaluated milk cartons. Parts or whole of the results of the model could be utilized, in order to facilitate the design process of novel milk cartons or the improvement of existing ones. According to the point of emphasis of the design team, certain inferences can be drawn to better understand consumers' feelings and translate them into design elements. The product properties of color, shape and material of a milk carton that were investigated here, move towards the direction of transparent material packaging solutions (e.g. plastic, glass), cylindrical shapes and light colors (e.g. white, green) for the product domain 'light-fresh milk' studied.

In regard with the kansei engineering process, an attempt to incorporate several techniques and methodologies, as the latter are applied within the consumer research field, was conducted. In particular, during the initial steps of the methodology, a 'mini netnographic' process was implemented in order to better define the product domain and collect all the available data for the formation of the semantic space. A focus group was conducted to achieve effective word reduction and to gain insights on the final selection of the kansei words. Depth interviews were carried out with the participants of the questionnaire survey in order to grasp their feelings about the methodology and to further comprehend the product domain and the findings of the netnographic process. As a result, the findings of the process were presented at a linear matrix where insights for both the kansei words and the product properties are drawn. A qualitative interpretation of the kansei

engineering process was conducted that aimed to identify participants' emotions and feelings and provide an explanation of the symbolic nature of these findings in relation with the product domain investigated.

Attempting to interpret emotions and to decode them into design elements is a complex process. Kansei engineering aims to link emotions with product properties, most commonly through the platform of words. The incorporation of qualitative methodologies from the lens of consumer research is argued to offer useful insights in order to achieve an effective, 'symbolic based', translation of consumers' feelings and emotions for products.

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